

STUDIES ON BASIC SULPHATES OF BIVALENT METALS. PART V. NICKEL

BY BARUN CHANDRA HALDAR

The basic sulphate $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NiO}$ has been found to exist by thermometric method.

Basic sulphates of nickel have not been studied in detail. From its position in the periodic table and its bivalent nature, it is expected to give basic sulphates either of the type $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{RO}$ or $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot \text{RO}$ or both, as in the case of other bivalent metals (Cu, Zn, Cd, Be). But literatures on basic sulphates of nickel do not state anything about the existence of the basic sulphate of the type $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{RO}$ or $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot \text{RO}$. Moreover, basic sulphates, stated to exist by different workers, do not agree with each other. Athanesco (*Compt. rend.*, 1886, 108, 271) claimed to have crystallised the compound $5\text{SO}_3 \cdot 6\text{NiO} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where nickel : hydroxide equals to 3:1. According to Pickering (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1985) the primary basic salt is $5\text{NiO} \cdot 3\text{SO}_3$ from which two other basic sulphates, namely $5\text{NiO} \cdot 2\text{SO}_3$ and $5\text{NiO} \cdot \text{SO}_3$, are formed successively and the last named one is the most stable. Again Gire (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 197, 1646) from the hydrolysis of nickel sulphate solution has concluded that the percentage of SO_3 in the basic salt, $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{NiO} \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is always less than that required by the above formula, the deficit increasing with washing. Thus, it is quite evident that the results of different workers do not agree with one another and it also appears that the basic sulphates of nickel, if they exist at all, are not very stable. So, in order to study the basic sulphate formation by nickel, it will not be judicious to remove the solid phase from the mother-liquor, because in that case, the solid phase may decompose and indicate the existence of a different compound. The best way to study such unstable systems will be by some physical method where removal of the solid phase from the mother-liquor is not required. The author has studied nickel sulphate-caustic soda system by thermometric method in continuation of his work on studies on basic sulphates of bivalent metals.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric apparatus is the same as that has been described in a previous paper (Haldar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 147). Reagents used were all of 'Analar' quality. Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime.

DISCUSSION

The basic sulphate of the type $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NiO}$ is formed by nickel and is clearly indicated by the sharp breaks in the temperature-concentration curves (Fig. 1). But this change appears only when caustic soda solution is added to nickel sulphate solution. In the reverse case i.e., when nickel sulphate solution is added to caustic soda solution no such breaks appear. This is due to the fact that nickel hydroxide, formation of which is indicated in all the cases, once formed, does not pass on to the basic sulphate

$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NiO}$ by reacting with further quantity of nickel sulphate and the basic sulphate $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NiO}$ is probably stable only in presence of excess of nickel sulphate. It is peculiar that no indication of any other basic sulphate formation, as reported by various workers previously, are obtained by the thermometric method.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE I

40 C. c. of 0.10590M-nickel sulphate soln. used NaOH soln. = 1.059 M.

NaOH soln. added	Temp. reading	Total rise in temp.
0 c. c.	4.140	0.000
1	4.080	.060
2	4.010	.130
3	3.960	.180
4	3.900	.240
5	3.850	.290
6	3.800	.340
7	3.765	.375
8	3.740	.400
9	3.730	.410
10	3.720	.420
11	3.710	.430
12	3.700	.440
13	3.690	.450
14	3.680	.460
15	3.670	.470
16	3.660	.480

TABLE II

40 C. c. of 0.06445M-nickel sulphate soln. used NaOH soln. = 0.5156 M.

NaOH soln. added.	Temp. reading	Total rise in temp.
0 c. c.	3.820	0.000
1	3.790	.030
2	3.750	.070
3	3.720	.100
4	3.680	.140
5	3.640	.180
6	3.610	.210
7	3.570	.250
8	3.540	.280
9	3.520	.300
10	3.500	.320
11	3.490	.330
12	3.480	.340
13	3.465	.355
14	3.455	.365
16	3.430	.390
18	3.410	.410
20	3.390	.430
22	3.370	.450
24	3.350	.470

TABLE III

40 C. c. of 0.20375M-nickel sulphate soln. used NaOH soln. = 1.0594 M.

NaOH soln. added.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c. c.	3.440	0.000
1	3.380	.060
2	3.320	.120
3	3.260	.180
4	3.200	.240
5	3.140	.300
6	3.080	.360
7	3.040	.400
8	2.990	.450
9	2.950	.490
10	2.900	.540
11	2.850	.590
12	2.805	.635
13	2.770	.670
14	2.750	.690
15	2.740	.700
16	2.740	.700
18	2.720	.720
20	2.710	.730
22	2.700	.740

TABLE IV

40 C. c. of 0.1262M-NaOH soln. nickel sulphate soln. = 0.6445 M.

Ni sulphate soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c. c.	4.870	0.000
1	4.790	.080
2	4.710	.160
3	4.640	.230
4	4.600	.270
5	4.570	.300
6	4.550	.320
7	4.530	.340
8	4.500	.370
9	4.480	.390
10	4.470	.400
11	4.440	.430
12	4.420	.450
13	4.400	.470
14	4.380	.490
15	4.360	.510
16	4.340	.530
17	4.320	.550
18	4.300	.570

TABLE V

40 c. c. of 0.1710M-NaOH soln. nickel sulphate solution = 0.6445M.

Ni sulphate soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c. c.	3.500	0.000
1	3.450	.050
2	3.390	.110
3	3.330	.170
4	3.270	.230
5	3.220	.280
6	3.200	.300
7	3.190	.310
8	3.180	.320
9	3.170	.330
10	3.170	.330
11	3.160	.340
13	3.150	.350
15	3.140	.360

The author's best thanks are due to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, Dr. és. Sc., F. N. I. for his keen interest, helpful suggestions and all laboratory facilities during the progress of the work.

GHOSH PROFESSOR'S LABORATORY,
CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA

Received April 29, 1948

PLATE I *Oscillographic pictures of discharge current.*